

ONE-DIMENSIONAL MODELING OF THE DYNAMICS OF DELAMINATION GROWTH

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ABSTRACT

The nature and speed of dynamic delamination growth associated with the postbuckling growth of a disbonded layer depend on a number of geometrical and material parameters. In catastrophic delamination growth under a fixed axial strain load in the base plate, there is an initial phase of relatively slow growth dominated by peeling action at the crack tip and characterized by an increasing growth speed which remains comparable to the flexural waves speeds. Subsequently, contact of crack surfaces occurs near the crack tip and delamination growth is then dominated by shear action. Crack growth accelerates rapidly with the speed eventually approaching the shear wave speed of the material. An approximate analysis of the delamination growth behavior in the second phase of catastrophic growth is presented on the basis of a global energy balance condition for the whole delamination model and a local crack growth condition at the crack tip.

1. INTRODUCTION

Delamination is a principal failure mechanism of laminated composite structures. Internal delamination growth, initiated by local buckling of a disbonded layer under bending or in-plane compression loads in a base laminate, may lead to catastrophic failure of the structure. Most of the previous analytical and computational studies on instability-related delamination growth (see, for example, numerous references cited in two recent survey articles [1,2]) were based on the results of (static) postbuckling analyses. Although these studies took into account the important effects of geometrical nonlinearity, they ignored the inertial effect, which may significantly affect the deflection and the force and moment resultants, particular in the boundary region of the delaminated layer. Various dynamic characteristics of delamination growth, including the crack growth speed, are not provided by the results of a static postbuckling analysis.

The dynamic growth problem of a thin-film, one-dimensional delamination model under a compressive axial load in the base plate was investigated in two recent papers [3,4]. In Ref. [3], a quasi-dynamic analysis, based on a global energy-balance condition, was used to obtain a closed-form analytical expression of the delamination growth speed when the base plate is subjected to a fixed compressive axial strain ϵ_0 at a level sufficiently large to initiate delamination growth. Later solutions obtained by finite-element analysis [4] show excellent agreement with the prediction of the quasi-dynamic analysis in cases when crack growth ends in a state of arrest. In the contrary case of

catastrophic delamination growth, the finite-element solution indicates that the quasi-dynamic solution is valid only in an initial phase of crack growth when the crack surface remains completely open. Subsequently, contact of crack surfaces occurs near the crack tip and afterwards the finite-element solution of the delamination growth speed is significantly greater than that of the quasi-dynamic solution.

In the present work, the quasi-dynamic analysis is modified to account for partial contact of the crack surfaces in the second phase of catastrophic delamination growth. The results of the modified analysis are closer to the finite-element solutions of Ref. [4]. It should be mentioned that the inertial effect associated with axial motion, which may contribute significantly to the local crack growth condition at fast rate of delamination growth, has been considered in the present paper but was ignored in the finite-element analysis of Ref. [4]. The finite-element analysis involves significantly greater computational effort. While the method allows for greater accuracy in characterizing the deflection of the layer, the resulting solutions may involve inter-penetration (i.e., negative separation) of the delaminated layer and the base plate. In contrast, the modified quasi-dynamic analysis involves physically admissible deflection functions and yields rational predictions of the catastrophic delamination growth with exceedingly small analytical and computational efforts.

2. FORMULATION

We consider a thin delaminated layer, of thickness h and initial length $2a_0$, disbonded from a thick homogeneous base plate. The delamination runs across the entire width of the plate, so that the geometry of the problem is independent of the z -coordinate (Fig. 1a). The thin layer buckles when the base plate is subjected to a compressive axial strain, ϵ_0 , equal to or exceeding the value $(\pi h/a_0)^2/12$ (the latter is the level of axial strain in the base plate corresponding to the local buckling of the delaminated layer when the layer is treated as a thin plate with clamped end edges at $x = \pm a_0$). Prior to the growth of the delamination, the postbuckling deformation of the layer is described by

$$w_0(x) = 2h \sqrt{(a_0/\pi h)^2 \epsilon_0 - 1/12} \{ (1 + \cos(\pi x/a_0)) \}, \quad (-a_0 < x < a_0) \quad (1)$$

where x is the axial coordinate originating from the midpoint of the layer. The static strain energy release rate G at the front of delamination may be determined by evaluating the J -integral around a path enclosing the crack tip [5]. This yields

$$G = \frac{Eh}{2(1-\nu^2)} \left\{ \epsilon_0 - \frac{1}{12} (\pi h/a_0)^2 \right\} \left\{ \epsilon_0 + \frac{1}{4} (\pi h/a_0)^2 \right\} \quad (2)$$

Delamination growth starts when ϵ_0 is sufficiently large so that G attains the specific fracture energy for unit area of growth, G^* . If the axial strain load ϵ_0 is maintained constant after the initiation of growth, then the deflection function $w(x, t)$ in the subsequent growth process is governed by the differential equation

$$D w_{,xxxx} + P(t) w_{,xx} + \rho h w_{,tt} = 0 \quad (-b(t) < x < b(t)) \quad (3)$$

where $D = Eh^3/\{12(1-\nu^2)\}$ is the bending rigidity, E and ν are the elastic moduli of the material, ρh is the mass per unit length of the delaminated layer which, at the current time t , has the length $2a(t)$. The interval $-b(t) < x < b(t)$ is the *non-contact* region of the crack surface, which may be a subregion of the current crack surface, $-a(t) < x < a(t)$. It is anticipated that the speed of crack growth is considerably smaller than the longitudinal wave speed. Hence the axial compressive load $P(t)$ does not depend appreciably on x .

The deflection function $w(x,t)$ must satisfy the following conditions

$$w(x, t) = w_{,x}(x, t) = 0, \quad \text{for } |x| \geq b(t) \quad (4)$$

$$w(x,0) = w_0(x), \quad w_{,t}(x,0) = 0, \quad \text{for } |x| \leq a_0 \quad (5)$$

where $w_0(x)$ is as defined by Eq. (1). Furthermore, a boundary condition for the axial displacement requires that

$$P(t) = \frac{Eh}{(1-\nu^2)} \left\{ \epsilon_0 - \frac{1}{4a(t)} \int_0^{2a(t)} (w_{,x})^2 dx \right\} \quad (6)$$

Finally, one has the delamination growth condition at the crack tip:

$$D (w_{,xx})^2 + \{Eh\epsilon_0^2/(1-\nu^2)\} [1 - (1-\nu^2) P(t)/(Eh\epsilon_0)]^2 = 2 G^* + \rho h \{(w_{,t})^2 + (u_{,t})^2\} \quad (7)$$

where $u(x,t)$ is the axial displacement function. This dynamic growth condition takes into account the inertial terms associated with the transverse and axial motions. As mentioned in Reference [3], the inertial term involving $w_{,t}^2$ always vanishes as a result of the boundary condition $w_{,x} = 0$ at the moving crack tip. The term involving $u_{,t}^2$ was not considered in Reference [3] because it is negligibly small for slow delamination growth at speeds comparable to flexural wave speeds in the layer. However, at fast delamination growth approaching the speed of shear waves, transverse motion of the delaminated layer affects only an interior segment of the layer (since the flexural wave speeds are much smaller than the speed of the shear wave) so that all terms in Eq. (7) involving transverse motion vanish at the crack tip. In this case Eq. (7) reduces to

$$\{Eh\epsilon_0^2/(1-\nu^2)\} [1 - (1-\nu^2) P(t)/(Eh\epsilon_0)]^2 = 2 G^* + \rho h (u_{,t})^2. \quad (8)$$

If the specific fracture energy G^* is assumed to be a material constant, then the time-dependent term involving the axial compression force $P(t)$ must be balanced by the inertial term involving $u_{,t}^2$. Hence the latter has a significant effect on the local growth condition at the crack tip.

We define a (non-dimensional) material parameter α by

$$\alpha = 12 \epsilon_0 (a_0/\pi h)^2. \quad (9)$$

Then, by equating G of Eq. (2) with the (constant) specific fracture energy G^* , we obtain

$$(\alpha - 1) (\alpha + 3) = 288 (1-\nu^2) G^* a_0^4 / (E h^5 \pi^4). \quad (10)$$

A quasi-dynamic analysis of delamination growth, based on a global energy balance condition and a static (postbuckling) deflection function $w(x, t)$ associated with the current delamination length $2a(t)$, predicts that, if $\alpha \geq 1.5$, then delamination growth under the fixed strain load ϵ_0 at first accelerates rapidly but eventually decelerates to a state of arrest. On the other hand, if $\alpha < 1.5$, then delamination growth under the fixed strain load continues indefinitely.

For the dynamic delamination problem defined in Ref. [3], Chen and Ngo [4] presented a finite-element analysis without using the quasi-dynamic approximation. The results for the growth speed and the dynamic deflection were found to be in excellent agreement with the quasi-dynamic solutions in the case $\alpha \geq 1.5$. For the case of catastrophic delamination growth ($\alpha < 1.5$), the finite-element solutions agree closely with the quasi-dynamic solution only in an initial period of delamination growth. Subsequently, contact of the crack surfaces occurs near the delamination front and the speed of crack growth becomes significantly greater than the corresponding result of the quasi-dynamic

solution.

The present analysis is concerned with an approximate solution of the dynamic growth behavior in the second phase of catastrophic delamination growth, i.e., for the case $\alpha < 1.5$ and when the crack surfaces contain contact segments $-a(t) \leq x \leq -b(t)$ and $b(t) \leq x \leq a(t)$ near the two ends of the delamination (Fig. 1b). In this second phase of growth, the crack growth speed, $2a'(t)$, is much greater than the rate of growth of the interior non-contact region, $2b'(t)$, because the latter speed remains comparable to the flexural wave speeds of the thin layer. We introduce the non-dimensional lengths $\xi(t)$ and $\eta(t)$ by

$$\xi(t) = b(t)/a_0, \quad \eta(t) = a(t)/a_0. \quad (11)$$

Then $\xi(t) = \eta(t)$ in the initial phase of slow growth whereas $\xi(t)$ becomes much smaller than $\eta(t)$ in the second phase of fast growth. Within the non-contact interval $-a_0 \xi(t) \leq x \leq a_0 \xi(t)$, the deflection of the disbonded layer may still be approximated by the sinusoidal function

$$w(x, t) = h A \{1 + \cos(\pi x/a_0 \xi)\}, \quad (12)$$

where the factor A is determined by the axial force $P(t)$ through Eq. (6). The axial load is closely approximated by the buckling load of a layer with length $2b(t)$ and with clamped end conditions, i.e.,

$$P(t) = D (\pi/a_0 \xi)^2 = Eh \epsilon_0 / \{(1-v^2) \xi^2 \alpha\}. \quad (13)$$

Equations (6) and (13) yield the non-dimensional amplitude A :

$$A = \{\eta(\alpha \xi^2 - 1)/(3\xi)\}^{1/2}. \quad (14)$$

In the following analysis, we use a global energy balance condition for the whole delamination model and a local crack growth condition at the crack tip to determine the two functions $\xi(t)$ and $\eta(t)$. When these two functions are obtained, Eq. (13) yields the axial load and Eqs. (12) and (14) give the deflection function in the non-contact segment of the delaminated layer.

3. ANALYSIS

In the second phase of catastrophic delamination growth, the crack surfaces are in contact near the crack tip. The axial velocity ($u_{,t}$) near the crack tip is related to the crack growth speed, $a_0 \eta'$, by the relation

$$u_{,t} = \{\epsilon_0 - (1-v^2) P/Eh\} a_0 \eta'(t). \quad (15)$$

Substituting Eqs. (10) and (15) into Eq. (8), one obtains the following expression for $(a_0 \eta')^2$:

$$(a_0 \eta')^2 = \{12E/(1-v^2)\rho\} [1 - (1-1/\alpha)(1+3/\alpha)(1-1/\alpha \xi^2)^{-2}] \quad (16)$$

As mentioned previously, in the initial phase of catastrophic delamination growth, the crack surface remains completely open (i.e., $\xi = \eta$) and the crack growth speed of the quasi-dynamic solution, given by a closed-form analytical expression (Eq. (24) of Ref. [3] with the factor $4\pi^2/3$ replaced by $\pi^2/3$ in view of bi-directional delamination growth), is in excellent agreement with the finite-element solutions of Ref. [4]. At the moment when crack growth changes from the initial phase to the second phase, the delamination length $a_0 \xi^*$ may be determined by equating Eq. (16) with the closed-form expression of $(a_0 \eta')^2$ according to the quasi-dynamic solution, and solving the

resulting equation for $\xi = \xi^*$:

$$\begin{aligned} & (2\alpha/3) (\pi^2 h/24a_0)^2 [(1-1/\alpha\xi^2)^2 - (1/\xi)(1-1/\alpha)^2 - (1-1/\alpha)(1+3/\alpha)(1-1/\xi)] \\ & = [1 - (1-1/\alpha)(1+3/\alpha)(1-1/\alpha\xi^2)^{-2}] [(1-1/\alpha\xi^2)^{-1} + 1 + (\pi^2/9 - 1/6) (1-1/\alpha\xi^2)]. \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

In the following analysis we consider specifically a delaminated layer with the initial length $2a_0 = 10 \pi h/3$ (which is close to $10h$). Then Eq. (17) yields $\xi^* = 1.4751, 1.8789, 2.4699$ and 3.6996 , respectively, for $\alpha = 1.1, 1.2, 1.3$ and 1.4 .

We next consider the global energy balance of the delamination model in the growth process. The analysis follows the procedure of Ref. [3], with appropriate modifications required to account for partial contact of the crack surface and the dependence of the amplitude function A on both ξ and η (Eq. (14)). The total amount of strain energy released in the growth process is found to be

$$\{Eha_0 \epsilon_0^2/(1-\nu^2)\} [\eta(1-1/\alpha\xi^2)^2 - (1-1/\alpha)^2]$$

A part of the released energy, with the amount

$$2(\eta-1) a_0 G^* = \{Eha_0 \epsilon_0^2/(1-\nu^2)\}(1-1/\alpha)(1+3/\alpha)(\eta-1)$$

is consumed as fracture energy for sustaining delamination growth. The remaining portion is changed into kinetic energy associated with the transverse velocity

$$w_{,t} = w_{,\xi} \xi'(t) + w_{,\eta} \eta'(t)$$

Substituting Eqs. (12) and (14) into the right hand of the last equation, and integrating $\rho h w_{,t}^2/2$ over the interval $-a_0 \xi \leq x \leq a_0 \xi$, we obtain the kinetic energy of the delaminated layer. The global energy balance condition then yields the following differential equation

$$\begin{aligned} & \{4\pi^2/3 - 5 + 12 (1-1/\alpha\xi^2)^{-2}\} \eta (a_0 \xi' / \pi c_0)^2 + 12\xi (1-1/\alpha\xi^2)^{-1} (a_0 \xi' / \pi c_0) (a_0 \eta' / \pi c_0) \\ & + (3\xi^2/\eta) (a_0 \eta' / \pi c_0)^2 = \eta(1-1/\alpha\xi^2)^2 - (1-1/\alpha)^2 - (1-1/\alpha)(1+3/\alpha)(\eta-1). \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where

$$c_0 = (\pi h/2a_0) [E/\{12(1-\nu^2)\rho\}]^{1/2}$$

is the speed of flexural waves propagating in the delaminated layer with a wave length $2a_0$. It should be mentioned that the kinetic energy associated with the axial velocity $u_{,t}$ has been neglected in considering the global energy balance because $u_{,t}$ is an order of magnitude smaller than $w_{,t}$.

The local crack growth condition of Eq. (16) and the global energy balance condition of Eq. (18) form a system of two nonlinear first order differential equations for the two unknown functions $\xi(t)$ and $\eta(t)$. This system of equation can be integrated by using the Runge-Kutta formula and the condition $\xi^* = \eta^*$ at the initial instant of the second phase of delamination growth. A simpler method is by substituting Eq. (16) into Eq. (18) to eliminate the time variable and to obtain a single first-order differential equation for the variable ξ , which is considered as a function of the independent variable η . The latter equation may be integrated by using the initial condition $\xi(\xi^*) = \xi^*$.

The resulting solution for the dependence of ξ on η is shown in Fig. 2 for the four values of α ($\alpha = 1.1, 1.2, 1.3$ and 1.4). The straight-line relation $\xi = \eta$ refers to the initial phase of growth when the crack remains completely open. After ξ and η attain the value ξ^* , the relation between the two non-dimensional length variables changes abruptly. Further increases in the delamination length are accompanied by small increases in the length of the non-contact region. Figure 3 shows the normalized delamination growth speed versus the crack length. The crack growth speed shows a drastic increase immediately after the transition from the initial phase of slow growth to the subsequent phase of fast growth. Thereafter, the speed continues to increase at a reduced rate of acceleration and eventually approaches the speed of the shear wave.

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Fig. 1: One-dimensional delamination model

Fig. 2: Non-contact length, $2b$, versus total crack length, $2a$

Fig. 3: Crack growth speed, $2\dot{a}$, versus crack length, $2a$